

Factors Affecting IFRS Application in Vietnam

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Abstract:

The objective of the thesis is to identify and measure the impact of these factors on the IFRS application in Vietnamese enterprises. The thesis combines both qualitative and quantitative research methods to build and test hypotheses, in which SmartPLS software is used to test the official research model. The results of the study show that behavioral factors influencing IFRS adoption include: Attitude, Perception of Social Pressure, Perception of Control, and Perception of Usefulness

Keywords: IFRS application

1. Introduction

Statistics of IFRS Foundation on IFRS.org website show that as of April 2020, 166 countries have been or are on the way to apply IFRS with total GDP accounting for 98.8% of global GDP, of which there are many countries in the continent. The most application of IFRS is Europe with 44 countries (out of 44 independent countries), followed by Africa (38 countries) and America (37 countries), Asia and Oceania (34 countries respectively).) and the Middle East (13 countries). It can be seen that in the face of the general trend of globalization, it is very urgent to find a unified language in accounting, particularly through the preparation of financial statements and information presentation. Although there are conflicting opinions as well as delay in applying IFRS in some countries such as the US, China or India, the positive effects of IFRS are undeniable and have been proven through studies. Research in the past two decades on IFRS application in individual countries or research by groups of countries around the world, such as:

- Applying IFRS reduces profit management: Barth et al (2008) Christensen et al (2015);
- Applying IFRS increases the relevance of information: Bartov et al (2005), Horton and Serafeim (2010), Barth et al (2012);
- Applying IFRS helps to recognize losses more accurately: Barth et al (2008), Chen et al (2010), Sun et al (2011), Christensen et al (2015);
- Applying IFRS increases the comparability of information: Joshi et al (2008); Li (2010)
- Applying IFRS to increase stock price and liquidity: Daske et al (2008), Barth et al (2014); Barth et al (2018).

Not only brings benefits to big countries, but also provides opportunities to improve the quality of information on financial statements for developing countries. For example, Dante et al. (2018) collected data between 2000 and 2016 of 2,458 companies from 13 emerging countries (including Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Malaysia, Mexico, Nigeria, Pakistan, Peru, Philippines, Poland, Russia, and South Africa) came to the conclusion that thanks to the IFRS, the information quality on the financial statements increased and the profit management was reduced. On the other hand, there are still mixed views on the application of IFRS, for example Verschoor (2010) raised concerns of the US Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) over the application of IFRS including: the appropriateness of IFRS for financial statements; Investors' understanding of IFRS and the difference to US GAAP (US technical expertise); IFRS has impact on tax laws and regulatory requirements; or the impact of IFRS on businesses, which includes changes in contracts, or corporate governance, and potential litigation. In fact, the US currently has not officially applied IFRS, so the issue of this

country's concern completely has a basis for Vietnam to refer to for the most complete preparation, in the context of time. In the coming time, IFRS will be applied.

The application of IFRS in Vietnam was mentioned a few years ago, but according to IFRS Foundation (on website ifrs.org), as of April 2020, Vietnam has not officially committed to do so. However, the Ministry of Finance has issued a draft of the Scheme on the application of international financial reporting standards (2019) and the official version of the Project is attached to Decision 345 / QD-BTC on March 16, 2020. The use of IFRS is a certainty. However, because IFRS is principally based, that is, applying IFRS depends a lot on the qualifications and skills of the accountants and auditors, this may arise challenges in the IFRS application process. According to a study by Nguyen Ngoc Hiep (2017) by the end of 2017, the number of enterprises that have applied IFRS is still not much, Vietnam has only about 17 enterprises that have published IFRS version financial statements. Therefore, the Ministry of Finance must carefully assess the needs as well as the capacity of the business to develop the most appropriate approach.

2. Literature review

2.1. Research on international factors

When studying the factors influencing the application of IFRS in developing countries, Zeghal and Mhadhbi (2006) examined five factors that play a decisive role in the application of IFRS including: economic development (increase GDP growth), educational attainment (based on literacy rates according to a study by Larsson - 2003), FDI attraction, Anglo-American cultural linkages (English-speaking or related countries) relationship with UK / US), and existence of capital markets. Secondary data collected by author is mainly from World Bank. Based on the selection from IASB website of developing countries (in Europe, America, Africa, Asia) then divided into 2 groups to study, including: 32 countries applying IFRS and 32 countries. not applicable at the time of 2003. Factors influencing the adoption of IFRS are capital markets, literacy, and Anglo-American culture.

Overall on factors affecting the accounting environment, Choi and Meek (2008) build a model of factors affecting the accounting system including 8 factors: financial resources, legal system, tax , the relationship between economics and politics, inflation, economic growth, education, and culture. According to Shima and Yang (2012), the model of Choi and Meek quite fully synthesizes the main factors affecting the accounting system, and are tested in many research models.

Inheriting from the above pattern, Shima and Yang (2012) used data sources related to 73 countries from 2000-2007, with the number of observations being 527, covering most countries on all continents but except for European Union (European Union). According to the authors, the EU was not included in this study because the EU was forced to apply IFRS in the member countries, regardless of business environment factors. The countries selected in this study are divided into 3 groups: not allowed (22 countries, including Vietnam), allowed or required (14 countries), required (37 countries). The quantitative analysis shows that except for the two negative factors, tax and inflation, the remaining factors have positive effects on IFRS application, including: the relationship between economy and politics (including the UK colonial factor and foreign trade relations with IFRS countries), dependence on external debt, and the legal system, economic development, literacy, and the uncertainty avoidance (ie the lower the degree of fear, the more likely the IFRS will be applied). Among these, according to the authors, the risk aversion is also related to cultural factors. The results also showed that the former UK colonies would, when applied, cost less to convert and be easier to enforce.

In a study of cultural differences, Fox et al (2013) used qualitative research methods, namely, the author interviewed by semi-structured questions with 32 people in the UK, Ireland (24 people in total) and Italy (8 people). In which the UK and Ireland are the countries that follow the common law school and Italy belongs to the civil law school (code law or civil law). Respondents include accountants, auditors, regulators, information users, the implementation time is quite long, from early 2006 to mid-2007, and conducted separately by two

groups of authors (including both British and Italian). Outcome: in addition to IFRS benefits, cultural differences create a cost-effective implementation of IFRS in Italy. The author also emphasizes that this study is useful for companies that haven't adopted IFRS yet. According to the group of authors, the country follows the civil law system (applying civil law, or the law), the accounting tends to be followed very high and accounting regulations are often included in national law. family. Conventional systems, by contrast, are often handled on a case-by-case basis with little specific regulation. As can be seen in the UK, because it is not regulated by law, the process of establishing technical expertise will be more open in Italy. For example, the study of Schultz and Lopez (2001) on the impact of culture on accounting, concluded that under the same given conditions, accountants in Germany and France estimate the value of the cost of insurance. higher practice than accountants in the UK, stemming from cultural characteristics, namely, conservatism that exists in the cultures of the countries of the continental European accountancy school. Zehri and Chouaibi (2013) inherited the method and hypothesis of Zeghal and Mhadhbi (2006) for the application of IFRS in developing countries, they emphasized that only studying the voluntary application of IFRS. Specifically, in addition to the re-examination of factors such as those of Zeghal and Mhadhbi (2006), they added two new elements, the legal and political system. The sample used is 74 countries divided into 2 groups, applied and not applied as of 2008. Result: Trends in voluntary IFRS adoption are often attributed to economic growth rates, legal systems. complete, and educational qualifications. Besides, there is the presence of a compulsive factor in the application, and countries with a complete legal system will be more inclined to apply. In another respect, Alon (2010) applied the institutional theory of Meyer and Rowan (1977) and the institutional isomorphic theory of DiMaggio and Powell (1983) on the application of IFRS. The author uses a quantitative research method, with secondary data from 71 countries, including 3 groups: not applicable (39 countries), allowing voluntary application (13 countries), mandatory application (19 country). According to Alon, in theory, institutional theory (in the scope of international research) aims for countries to seek legitimacy and act on their need to legalize their systems. The author concludes that countries with weak and underdeveloped governance mechanisms will tend to institutionalize the financial statements through the application to achieve legitimacy (legitimacy). In contrast, countries that have already established good governance mechanisms, the need for IFRS application tends to be lower. In addition, high nationalist countries tend to refuse IFRS and prefer to use domestic standards.

2.2. Research on domestic factors

Research by Bessieux-Ollier and Walliser (2012) on voluntary adoption of 85 French companies listed on the Alternext market (the market for small and medium companies) in 2010, including 32 companies that applied IFRS (full IFRS, not IFRS for small and medium companies) and 53 companies used the domestic standard. The authors have collected secondary data in their annual reports, to test the following factors: financial leverage (based on Agency Theory Representative Theory by Jensen and Meckling, 1976). ; firm size (based on political cost theory); degree of internationalization (with export or international listing); profit; career; reputation of the audit company (whether in the Big 4 group or not); owner (less the owner, less voluntarily); and finally, the value of fixed assets. Outcome: high size (based on assets) and high value of fixed assets will influence voluntary adoption. In particular, the authors emphasized that, if there is no "force" from the regulatory body, companies on the Alternext floor will continue to apply domestic standards.

Research by Şenyiğit (2014) in Turkey during the voluntary application period of 2003-2004 (right before the time when the European Union forced IFRS) of a total of 206 enterprises on the exchange Bora Istanbul (including 61 companies applied and 145 not yet applied, a total of these 2 groups account for 72% of listed companies). Outcome: Factors influencing IFRS adoption are size, export performance, and audit firm. The author noted that the financial institutions have fundamental differences from the other group, so they are not included in the study.

In addition to researching the application situation in Europe or developed countries, according to Lin (2012), research in less developed countries is also essential. Because applying IFRS in these countries will reduce the asymmetry of information between enterprises and foreign investors, thereby attracting FDI will be easier,

investors will easily grasp the opportunities. to thrive in these countries. For example, the study of Bova and Pereira (2012) on the case of applying IFRS in Kenya, a country which is considered by the author to have weak enforcement environment. Even though it is a developing country, Kenya has forced all types of companies (including small and medium companies) to apply international standards since 1999. The authors collect secondary data from financial statements during the period 2005. -2007 of 78 companies. Results: listed companies performed better IFRS compliance than private firms due to better capacity. Foreign ownership has a positive and significant correlation with compliance with international standards, which is also relevant where foreign investors are exposed to a higher risk of information asymmetry, thus demanding ask for higher quality financial statements through IFRS compliance. And, the more IFRS-compliant a company is, the more liquid is the stock.

2.3. Research using behavioral theory

Mir and Rahaman (2004) use the theory of Institutional Isomorphism DiMaggio and Powell (1983) to explore the process of applying IAS in Bangladesh. The method they used was mostly interviewing. During the last 5 weeks of 1999 and early 2000, the authors conducted the first 22 interviews. From late 2003 to mid-2004, there were 5 more interviews to complete the survey. All 27 interviews were recorded. Participants included 8 policy makers of the Bangladesh Institute of Chartered Accountants (ICAB), 2 people from the Bangladesh Securities Commission, 6 senior experts from listed companies, 5 senior auditors, 2 banking experts, 1 researcher at university, 3 experts from Bangladesh Institute of Accounting and Costing Management (ICMAB). Each interview lasted from 30 minutes to 1 hour, to identify advantages and problems encountered in the application process. In addition, the study also exploited information on annual reports for the fiscal year ended June 2000 of 13 enterprises from different sectors. According to the authors group, the policy-making organizations applying IAS in Bangladesh include: Government (represented by the Securities Commission), World Bank, Asian Development Bank ADB, and Institute of Chartered Accountants. Bangladesh, in which the World Bank funded the Government 200,000 USD in August 1999 to develop the standard system of Accounting and Auditing in Bangladesh. The results show that the main driving force for IAS adoption is the institutional legalization factor, due to the pressure to receive funding or loans from abroad on the Bangladeshi government and pressure from professional associations.

In the Malaysian readiness study to apply full IFRS from 1 January 2012, Phang and Mahzan (2013) collected 150 responses / 859 questionnaires sent to the CFO, Chief Accountant of Malaysian Listed Companies. This study has applied the theory of institutional isomorphism of DiMaggio and Powell (1983) as the theoretical basis. The mean values of the responses showed that stakeholder pressure, especially regulatory forces, had the strongest impact on IFRS adoption. The results show that the legitimate effects of society - external factors, particularly coercive forces (the author is called Coercive forces from stakeholders), simulation pressure (Imitation tendencies in organisation field and professional pressure (Participation in accounting professional bodies), these are the main factors influencing the adoption .

Also in a study on Bangladesh, Nurunnabi (2015) when discussing institutional impact on IFRS adoption in Bangladesh used qualitative research, through two interviews with founders. financial statements, accountants, researchers, and users in 2010 and 2011; combined with document analysis methods in the period 1998-2010. As a result, institutional pressure (or pressure), simulation pressure, and expertise have no significant impact on adoption in these countries, due to poor enforcement and of political factors.

At the national level, in a study Pricope (2016) from data from 97 developing countries (including 70 that have adopted and 27 that have not as of 2013), it is concluded that, Simulation pressure plays a very important role in promoting the application of IFRS in these countries, however professional pressure and coercive pressure have no significant impact.

Aburous (2018) research on IFRS implementation in Jordan creates a power imbalance between corporate accountants and auditors, and changes familiar accounting practices. . The reason for this study is because the

author thinks that there is a large difference in understanding between the accounting and auditing groups for IFRS. According to Aburous's synthesis, institutional theory was formulated in 1977 by Meyer and Rowan, on that basis, in 2006 Lawrence and Suddaby developed the concept of "institutional activity" to explain the institutionalization of exports. emanating from day-to-day operations of an organization, and institutional work are the purposeful actions of the individual and the organization to create, maintain, and destroy the organization itself. Organizational creation is the building of rules, identities and values, while destruction involves destroying the tools used to support compliance within the institution. The focus of this paper is research on the remainder of the institutional activity that is the institutional maintenance of accounting in firms, and on the other hand, the sustained institutionalization of IFRS. This study argues that application is due to coercive pressures and specialized pressures (also known as normative pressures). In particular, coercive pressure is exerted by powerful countries, and transnational institutions, in the form of: recommendations, conditions in business agreements, credit ratings, and economic, political; also and the professional pressure comes from multinational auditing firms. According to the author, from the application stage to the implementation of IFRS, the papers research the accountant's behavior and the potential consequences are still limited. The author has analyzed the accountant's work interpretation to understand how they have dealt with IFRS-related issues. In which, open questions, not completely fixed (using semi-structured questions) are used with each person, the object is 22 people who work as accountants of the business (accountants, chief accountants, directors finance, financial management) in many sectors and 5 senior auditors (of which 3 are multinational and 2 are domestic) in 2012. Scale of Companies selected for interviews included small (under 20 employees), medium, and large (per 100 employees). In addition, the author also conducted an additional interview with 2 experts of the Jordan Stock Exchange, and 3 interviews with university lecturers. Duration of each interview is 40-110 minutes and recorded. One of the notable answers that the author listed was that of a CFO of a large manufacturing company: "Perhaps this is my fault (of understanding), in the new meeting. Mostly with the auditor, I have seen the audit report and asked about the auditor's IFRS mentioned. I realize everything has changed (in accounting policy) and I don't know anything about it. I feel like I'm being left behind. Even a chief accountant of a large technology company answered that she did not know that her company must comply with IFRS, although it is mentioned in the company's financial statements. At a lower level, a company's accountant believes that IFRS training and implementation is not focused in Jordan, as there is no specialized agency to do this. There is an opinion that the authorities only focus on corporate income tax instead of training and policies to promote application. The auditors in the interviews also admitted that the accountants did not receive sufficient preparation of knowledge or detailed instructions to apply. The mismatch in the qualifications and knowledge of auditors and accountants about IFRS is synthesized through the answer "accountants handle simple operations, the rest (complex operations). has an audit company in charge ".

3. Research method

In order to match the new research objective which is to determine the influencing factors and the influence level of the factors, the thesis is done by a mixed method and is done in two phases: preliminary stage and stage. official passage. The objective of the preliminary study is to adjust the scale, in which interviewing experts to complete the draft scale; then conduct a test survey to verify the scale. The results of the preliminary study are a calibrated scale for use in the official research stage. More specifically, the preliminary research phase includes qualitative research with experts in the accounting field by conducting in-depth interviews with managers and understanding of corporate accounting, lecturers, and auditors. accountants have experience in accounting and auditing, and IFRS drafting experts in Vietnam to adjust the scale; and then preliminary quantitative research to test the scale. In the next step, the thesis carries out official quantitative research to test the research hypotheses.

In particular, the quantitative research will focus on analyzing data with Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) technique to identify the factors that are to the application of IFRS in Vietnam. This is a technique that has been widely used in behavioral science since the end of the last century (Ajzen, 1991) until

now. Basically, PLS-SEM is a combination of factor analysis and regression, however, it can solve the complex relationships in the research model well compared to regression analysis. This analysis technique is very suitable for the complex model used in this thesis, especially in the model with many relationships to test, including direct and indirect relationships. In addition, PLS-SEM is also a trend to analyze many applied studies in recent period (Hair et al., 2017), including studies in the accounting field in Vietnam and internationally.

The study will use SmartPLS software version 3.2.8 to test scales and hypotheses, thereby clarifying research questions. In addition, the thesis will also use G * power software as an additional tool to determine the appropriate sample size.

The source of data used will be primary data collected by the author through direct interviews in the qualitative research section with experts and through surveys sent to businesses at step preliminary research and formal quantitative research.

Research models

4. Result

Table 1. Cronbach's Alpha spreadsheet and Comprehensive reliability

Scale	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
ACC	0.729	0.831
ACM	0.802	0.871
AD	0.838	0.904
AMP	0.819	0.882
AXH	0.858	0.904
DK	0.776	0.870
HI	0.831	0.876
KS	0.779	0.871
NL	0.707	0.837
TD	0.830	0.887

Table 2. Fornell-Larcker numerical spreadsheet

	ACC	ACM	AD	AMP	AXH	DK	HI	KS	NL	TD
ACC	0.810									
ACM	0.708	0.793								
AD	0.615	0.643	0.872							
AMP	0.644	0.601	0.546	0.883						
AXH	0.633	0.686	0.696	0.570	0.838					
DK	0.434	0.599	0.724	0.495	0.673	0.832				
HI	0.565	0.596	0.715	0.430	0.615	0.583	0.773			
KS	0.574	0.502	0.507	0.503	0.524	0.529	0.376	0.832		
NL	0.586	0.573	0.685	0.524	0.671	0.628	0.602	0.678	0.795	
TD	0.498	0.598	0.735	0.419	0.595	0.598	0.743	0.345	0.504	0.815

Table 3. Table of calculation of cross load factor

	ACC	ACM	AD	AMP	AXH	DK	HI	KS	NL	TD
ACC1	0.800	0.551	0.59	0.498	0.532	0.439	0.533	0.368	0.457	0.506
ACC2	0.788	0.549	0.377	0.552	0.376	0.241	0.358	0.406	0.371	0.321
ACC3	0.842	0.616	0.498	0.53	0.59	0.347	0.459	0.595	0.562	0.368
ACM1	0.439	0.745	0.478	0.44	0.478	0.429	0.355	0.299	0.356	0.48
ACM2	0.556	0.866	0.523	0.41	0.559	0.533	0.532	0.401	0.455	0.515
ACM3	0.485	0.815	0.541	0.397	0.513	0.545	0.527	0.288	0.399	0.536
ACM4	0.724	0.739	0.492	0.63	0.606	0.395	0.461	0.564	0.574	0.375
AD1	0.551	0.614	0.943	0.54	0.669	0.727	0.67	0.409	0.63	0.731
AD2	0.559	0.548	0.911	0.46	0.619	0.657	0.726	0.371	0.618	0.692
AD3	0.500	0.519	0.749	0.423	0.524	0.488	0.446	0.586	0.542	0.473
AMP1	0.672	0.58	0.512	0.889	0.513	0.413	0.402	0.488	0.469	0.335
AMP2	0.586	0.559	0.497	0.934	0.527	0.491	0.356	0.465	0.545	0.366
AMP3	0.438	0.446	0.432	0.821	0.467	0.405	0.382	0.372	0.362	0.415
AXH1	0.444	0.622	0.637	0.482	0.811	0.648	0.534	0.424	0.558	0.468
AXH2	0.561	0.604	0.564	0.423	0.883	0.554	0.622	0.376	0.593	0.612
AXH3	0.517	0.456	0.531	0.457	0.794	0.481	0.399	0.429	0.476	0.413
AXH4	0.599	0.602	0.594	0.543	0.86	0.559	0.495	0.523	0.609	0.494
DK1	0.287	0.433	0.539	0.339	0.547	0.847	0.388	0.46	0.465	0.38
DK2	0.374	0.534	0.528	0.381	0.543	0.869	0.467	0.464	0.548	0.477
DK3	0.436	0.536	0.77	0.538	0.597	0.775	0.624	0.389	0.563	0.663
HI1	0.452	0.501	0.59	0.31	0.468	0.483	0.758	0.317	0.513	0.573
HI2	0.326	0.386	0.604	0.255	0.487	0.517	0.802	0.295	0.435	0.591
HI3	0.423	0.397	0.531	0.266	0.436	0.411	0.811	0.301	0.453	0.646
HI4	0.475	0.528	0.458	0.289	0.366	0.313	0.732	0.193	0.411	0.437
HI6	0.523	0.515	0.559	0.537	0.6	0.498	0.757	0.328	0.506	0.596
KS1	0.581	0.449	0.479	0.554	0.418	0.375	0.365	0.799	0.632	0.315
KS2	0.323	0.351	0.352	0.261	0.343	0.43	0.218	0.835	0.462	0.254
KS3	0.493	0.438	0.417	0.401	0.529	0.514	0.335	0.861	0.574	0.282
NL1	0.489	0.55	0.609	0.51	0.563	0.549	0.476	0.479	0.715	0.463
NL2	0.441	0.383	0.522	0.319	0.511	0.442	0.51	0.545	0.849	0.367
NL3	0.472	0.448	0.517	0.433	0.533	0.515	0.455	0.587	0.816	0.384
TD1	0.405	0.52	0.569	0.273	0.402	0.5	0.538	0.287	0.353	0.727
TD2	0.391	0.496	0.627	0.364	0.516	0.525	0.561	0.331	0.385	0.818
TD3	0.411	0.458	0.573	0.404	0.575	0.484	0.631	0.313	0.492	0.853
TD4	0.416	0.479	0.626	0.323	0.445	0.446	0.682	0.201	0.41	0.855

Table 4. Assessment results of relationships with total impacts (direct and indirect)

Mối quan hệ	Hệ số tác động	Độ lệch chuẩn	Thống kê T	P Values
ACC -> AD	0.050	0.024	2.084	0.037
ACC -> AXH	0.200	0.071	2.806	0.005
ACM -> AD	0.114	0.035	3.239	0.001
ACM -> AXH	0.457	0.071	6.441	0.000
AMP -> AD	0.060	0.028	2.108	0.035
AMP -> AXH	0.240	0.080	2.994	0.003
AXH -> AD	0.248	0.069	3.608	0.000
DK -> AD	0.078	0.038	2.043	0.041
DK -> KS	0.343	0.122	2.824	0.005
HI -> AD	0.431	0.064	6.746	0.000
HI -> TD	0.760	0.035	21.656	0.000
KS -> AD	0.229	0.062	3.690	0.000
NL -> AD	0.112	0.035	3.247	0.001
NL -> KS	0.491	0.094	5.232	0.000
TD -> AD	0.290	0.076	3.791	0.000

5. Conclusion

In practical terms, the research results of the thesis have shown that behavioral factors contribute to the application of IFRS in businesses, thereby helping the regulators to adopt IFRS in Viet Nam. It can be seen that the most important factor driving IFRS application is Attitude at 0.29 level, higher than the other two factors. Thus, once businesses have a positive attitude towards IFRS, their motivation for adoption will become clearer. To do this, it is necessary for the managers to understand the role and necessity of IFRS for the business.

Next, corporate awareness of social pressure also plays an important role in applying IFRS with the impact level of 0.248. Perception of social pressure is influenced by three factors. Coercive pressure, simulation pressure, and professional pressure. Inside:

- Coercive pressure is when businesses are aware of the pressure / incentives from the regulators to apply IFRS, this will change their perception and thereby influence perceptions. Thus, in order to successfully apply IFRS, the Ministry of Finance needs to have a special incentive and appropriate support mechanism for businesses, especially during the voluntary application phase, how do they see it? benefits and understand the corporate responsibility in applying IFRS.
- For simulation pressure, research results show that firms tend to look at companies in the same field, especially leading companies, and multinational corporate models to follow. as a general trend. Thus, when the IFRS application becomes more popular, businesses that have not yet applied will also tend to follow suit. This is the basis for the regulators to have a mechanism to encourage industry leaders in the fields to pioneer in applying IFRS to create spillovers.
- The impact of professional pressure on Perceptions of social pressure shows that for accountants, career trends also play a key role to change their perception. Accounting is one of the professions with strongly developed professional organizations, both domestically and internationally. In fact, in Vietnam, international professional associations play a very good role in connecting regulators and businesses. This shows that the professional association is a very useful channel that regulators should pay attention to when building a roadmap for IFRS application in Vietnam, when the orientation of these organizations can also contribute to the determine career trends, thereby changing enterprises' perceptions of the importance of IFRS.

Finally, in order to apply IFRS successfully, it is impossible to ignore the perception of control, including resources (considered as internal elements of the business) and objective external conditions required to apply. Use IFRS.

- Building a team of qualified accountants is very important for successful IFRS application. In the qualitative survey, most expert opinion emphasized the need to invest in human resources, once knowledge about IFRS has been widely updated, in which training institutions play the role. In a very important role, the application of IFRS will no longer be a major barrier. In fact, when Circular 200/2014 / TT-BTC was born with many changing requirements in accounting, it also led to certain difficulties in the early implementation, thanks to the timely update. Simultaneously and synchronously in training programs, this circular has been increasingly applied even in small and medium enterprises. The release of this circular is also a very important stepping stone for IFRS application. When enterprises and accountants understand that IFRS is not a change to the entire current accounting policy, but there is a preparation step to pass Circular 200, the application will become easier. However, it cannot be denied that the application of IFRS also requires a large initial investment as well as a close coordination among departments in the business, because the information requested by IFRS is not only related. accounting, but also information on very important areas such as business, personnel policy, etc.
- For objective factors outside the enterprise, consistency in the management policy of accounting and the synchronization with the tax policy is required. The report on impact assessment of the application of IFRS in Vietnam (attached to Decision 345 / QD-BTC) also gave a very suitable opinion with the research results on the objective factors mentioned in the thesis. That is, the ability to apply IFRS depends not only on the business but also influenced by external factors. Specifically, in Vietnam, the accounting work is affected by accounting standards, tax policies and financial mechanisms, leading to an overlap, inconsistency in the way of approaching and applying policies that lead to There are many difficulties for businesses and for State management agencies themselves because the compliance inspection and monitoring mechanism is not good, making the transparency and comparability of domestic financial statements not high. Similarly, the opinion World Bank made in the Report assessing the compliance with standards and rules in the field of accounting and auditing in Vietnam (2016) shows that the financial statements of some financial institutions and home enterprises Vietnam is presented on the basis of prioritizing compliance with sector-specific financial regulations issued by the Government over compliance with technical expertise.
- Another note for the application of IFRS in Vietnam is that the guiding documents need to be complete, detailed and timely. In particular, it is necessary to study and promulgate detailed guidance circulars on IFRSs, because many studies around the world have shown that the absence of IFRS guidelines has caused many difficulties for businesses. This is mentioned in the studies of Bahadir et al (2016), by Jermakowicz and Gornick-Tomaszewski (2006), or by Aburous (2018). This is also acknowledged in the impact assessment report on the application of IFRS in Vietnam (attached to decision 345 / QD-BTC) on working culture based on detailed instructions in Vietnam can cause problems. difficulties in the early stages if only applying IFRS without specific instructions.

References

- i. *Abd-Elsalam, O. H. & Weetman, P. (2003). Introducing International Accounting Standards to an emerging capital market: relative familiarity and language effect in Egypt. Journal of International Accounting, Auditing & Taxation, 12, 63–84.*
- ii. *Aburous, D. (2018). IFRS and institutional work in the accounting domain. Critical Perspectives on Accounting, 62(C), 1-15.*
- iii. *Ahalik (2016). The relationship of theory of planned behaviour and Ifrs knowledge of Indonesian accountants. International Journal of Applied Business and Economics Research, 14(6), 4493-4505*
- iv. *Ajzen, I. (1985). From intentions to actions: A theory of planned behavior. In J. Kuhl & J. Beckmann (Eds.), Action-control: From cognition to behavior (11-39). Heidelberg: Springer.*

- v. Ajzen, I. (1991). *The Theory of Planned Behavior*. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), 179-211
- vi. Ajzen, I. (2001) *Nature and operation of attitudes*, *Annual Review of Psychology*, 52, 27-58.
- vii. Akpomi, M.E. & Nnadi, M.A. (2017). *The impact of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) adoption on Foreign Direct Investments (FDI): Evidence from Africa and implications for managers of education*. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*, 3(2), 51-65
- viii. Alon, A. (2010). *Three studies related to the institutionalization of International Financial Reporting Standards (2010)*. *Electronic Theses and Dissertations*.
- ix. Alp, A., & Ustundag, S. (2009). *Financial reporting transformation the experience of Turkey*. *Critical Perspective on Accounting*, 20, 680-699.
- x. André, P., Walton, P., Dan, Y. (2012), *Voluntary adoption of IFRS: A study of determinants for UK unlisted firms*. *Comptabilités et Innovation*, May 2012, Grenoble, France.
- xi. Armitage, C.J. (2001). *Efficacy of the Theory of Planned Behaviour: A meta-analytic review*. *British Journal of Social Psychology*, 40, 471–499.
- xii. Armstrong C. S., Barth M. E., Jagolinzer A. D. & Riedl E. J. (2010). *Market Reaction to the Adoption of IFRS in Europe*. *The accounting review*, 85(1), 31–61.
- xiii. Bahadır O., Demir V. & Oncel A. G. (2016). *IFRS Implementation in Turkey: Benefits and Challenges*. *Journal of Accounting and Management Information Systems*, 15(1), 5-26.
- xiv. Barth, M. E., Landsman, W. R., & Lang, M. H. (2008). *International accounting standards and accounting quality*. *Journal of Accounting Research* 46 (3): 467– 498.
- xv. Barth, M. E., Landsman, W.R., Lang, M.H., & Williams, C. D. (2018). *Effects on Comparability and Capital Market Benefits of Voluntary IFRS Adoption*. *Rock Center for Corporate Governance at Stanford University Working Paper No. 133*.
- xvi. Barth, M.E., Landsman, W.R., Lang, M., & Williams, C. (2012). *Are IFRS-based and US GAAP-based accounting amounts comparable?* *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 54, 68–93.
- xvii. Barth, M.E., Landsman, W.R., Young, D., & Zhuang, Z. (2014). *Relevance of differences between net income based on IFRS and domestic standards for European firms*. *Journal of Business Finance and Accounting*, 43, 297–327.
- xviii. Bartov, E., Goldberg, S.R., & Kim, M. (2005). *Comparative value relevance among German, U.S., and International Accounting Standards: A German stock market perspective*. *Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance*, 20, 95–119.
- xix. Bessieux-Ollier, C. & Walliser, E. (2012). *Why firms listed on an unregulated financial market comply voluntarily with IFRS: An empirical analysis with French data*. *Comptabilités et innovation*, May 2012, Grenoble, France.
- xx. Bobek, D. D. & Hatfield, R. C. (2003) *An Investigation of the Theory of Planned Behavior and the Role of Moral Obligation in Tax Compliance*. *Behavioral Research in Accounting*, 15(1), 13-38.
- xxi. Bova, F. & Pereira, R. (2012). *The Determinants and Consequences of Heterogeneous IFRS Compliance Levels Following Mandatory IFRS Adoption: Evidence from a Developing Country*. *Journal of International Accounting Research*, 11(1), 83–111.
- xxii. Bozkurt, O., Islamolu, M. & Oz, Y. (2013). *Perceptions of professionals interested in accounting and auditing about acceptance and adaptation of global financial reporting standards*. *Journal of Economics, Finance and Administrative Science*, 18, 16-23.
- xxiii. Chen, H., Tang, Q., Jiang, Y. & Lin, Z. (2010). *The Role of International Financial Reporting Standards in Accounting Quality: Evidence from the European Union*. *Journal of International Financial Management & Accounting*, 21(3).
- xxiv. Cheng, X. (2017). *Applying the Theory of Planned Behavior to Influence Auditors' Knowledge-Sharing Behavior*. *Graduate Theses and Dissertations*.
- xxv. Choi, F. & Meek, G. (2008). *International Accounting*, 7th ed. Pearson Prentice Hall.

- xxvi. Christensen, H.B., Lee, E., Walker, M., & Zeng, C. (2015). Incentives or standards: What determines accounting quality changes around IFRS adoption. *European Accounting Review*, 24(1), 31–61.
- xxvii. Churchill, G. A. Jr (1979). A paradigm for developing better measures of marketing constructs. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 26 (1), 64-73.
- xxviii. Chwelos, P., Benbasat, I., & Dexter, A.S. (2001). Research report: empirical test of an EDI adoption model. *Information Systems Research*, 12 (3), 304–321.
- xxix. Cooper, G. (2016) *Using an Extended Theory of Planned Behavior Model to Investigate Students' Intentions to Enrol in University*. Doctoral thesis RMIT University.
- xxx. Corbin, J. & Strauss, A. (1990). *Basics of qualitative research: Grounded theory procedures and techniques*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- xxxi. Dang Duc Son (2011). Compliance with accounting standards by SMEs in transitional economies: evidence from Vietnam. *Journal of Applied Accounting Research*, 12 (2), 96-107.
- xxxii. Dante, B C V J, Ohlson, M P, Lourenço, I, Gerlando, A S F D L (2018). Mandatory adoption of IFRS and earnings management in emerging countries: the role of national culture. XVIII Usp International Conference IN Accounting.
- xxxiii. Daske, H., Hail, L., Leuz, C., Verdi R. (2008). Mandatory IFRS Reporting Around the World: Early Evidence on the Economic Consequences. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 46(5), 1085-1142.
- xxxiv. Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, and User Acceptance of Information Technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 13(3), 319-340.
- xxxv. Davis, F. D., Bagozzi, R. P., & Warshaw, P. R. (1989). User Acceptance Of Computer Technology: A Comparison Of Two Theoretical Models. *Management Science*, 35(8), 982-1003.
- xxxvi. De George E.T., Li X. & Shivakumar L. (2016) A review of the IFRS adoption literature. *Review of Accounting Studies*, 21 (3). 898-1004.
- xxxvii. De George, E. T., Ferguson C, Spear N. (2013), How Much Does IFRS Cost? IFRS Adoption and Audit Fees. *Accounting Review*, 88(2), 2013.
- xxxviii. DiMaggio, P. & Powell, W. (1983). The Iron Cage Revisited: Institutional Isomorphism and Collective Rationality in Organizational Fields. *American Sociological Review*, 48(2), 147-160.
- xxxix. Djatej, A, Zhou, D, Gorton, D & McGonigle, W. (2012), "Critical Factors of IFRS Adoption in the US: An Empirical Study", *Journal of Finance and Accountancy*, 1 (14)
- xl. Ehoff, Jr., C., & Fischer, D. (2013). Why The SEC Is Delaying Adoption Of International Financial Reporting Standards. *International Business & Economics Research Journal (IBER)*, 12(2), 223-228.
- xli. Elbakry, A. E., Nwachukwu, J. C., Abdou, H. A., & Elshandidy, T. (2017). Comparative evidence on the value relevance of IFRS-based accounting information in Germany and the UK. *Journal of International Accounting, Auditing, and Taxation*, 28, 10–30.
- xl.ii. Faul F., Erdfelder E., Lang A-G. & Buchner A. (2007). G*Power 3: A flexible statistical power analysis program for the social, behavioral, and biomedical sciences. *Behavior Research Methods*, 39, 175–191
- xl.iii. Fearnley, S. & Hines, T., (2007). How IFRS has destabilised financial reporting for UK non-listed entities. *Journal of Financial Regulation and Compliance*, 15(4), 394 – 408.
- xl. iv. Florou, A & Pope, P.F. (2012) Mandatory IFRS Adoption and Institutional Investment Decisions. *The Accounting Review*, 87 (6), 1993-2025
- xl. v. Fox, A, Hannah, G., Helliari, C., & Veneziani M. (2013). The costs and benefits of IFRS implementation in the UK and Italy, *Journal of Applied Accounting Research*, 14 (1), 86-101.
- xl. vi. Gassen, J. & T. Sellhorn (2006). Applying IFRS in Germany: Determinants and consequences, *Betriebswirtschaftliche Forschung und Praxis*. 58 (4), 365-386.
- xl. vii. Greaves, M., Zibarras, L.D. & Stride, C. (2013) Using the theory of planned behavior to explore environmental behavioral intentions in the workplace. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 34, 109-120.
- xl. viii. Hair, J. F. Jr., Hult, G. T. M, Ringle, C., & Sarstedt, M. (2017). *A primer on partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM), 2e*: Sage Publications

- xlix. Hair, J. F. Jr., Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C., & Gudergan S. P. (2018). *Advanced Issues in Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling*. Sage Publications.
- l. Hambrick, D. C., & Mason, P. A. (1984). Upper echelons: The organization as a reflection of its top managers. *Academy of Management Review*, 9: 193-206.
- li. Haveman, H.A. (1993). Follow the leader: mimetic isomorphism and entry into new markets. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 38 (4), 593–627.
- lii. Hope, O–K., Jin, J., & Kang, T. (2006). Empirical evidence on jurisdictions that adopt IFRS. *Journal of International Accounting Research*, 5(2), 1-20.
- liii. Horton, J. & Serafeim G. (2010), 'Market reaction to and valuation of IFRS reconciliation adjustments: First evidence from the UK. *Review of Accounting Studies*, 15, 725-751.
- liv. Hung, M. & Subramanyam, K.R. (2007). Financial statement effects of adopting international accounting standards: The case of Germany. *Review of Accounting Studies*, 12, 623–657.
- lv. Huynh Tan Dung, Doan Van Dinh & Gong Guang Ming (2012). Vietnamese Accounting System Reform – Review and Prospect. *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 6(9): 629-651.
- lvi. ICAEW (2007). *EU implementation of IFRS and the fair value directive: A report for the European Commission*.
- lvii. IFRS Foundation (2018). *Use of IFRS Standards around the world*. Retrieved on June 7, 2020.
- lviii. Jensen, M.C. & Meckling, W.H. (1976), *Theory of the firm: managerial behavior, agency costs and ownership structure*, *Journal of Financial Economics*, 305 – 360.
- lix. Jermakowicz, E. K. & Gornik-Tomaszewski, S. (2006). Implementing IFRS from the perspective of EU publicly traded companies. *Journal of International Accounting, Auditing and Taxation*, 15, 170–196
- lx. Joshi, P.L., Bremser, W.G. & Al-Ajmi, J. (2008). Perceptions of accounting professionals in the adoption and implementation of a single set of global accounting standards: Evidence from Bahrain. *Advances in Accounting*, 24 (1), 41-48.
- lxi. Kurt, G. & Ucma, T. (2013). *Convergence IFRS in Turkey: Insights and Evidence from Academicians and Practitioners*. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*. 4 (4).
- lxii. Kvaal E. & Nobes C. (2010). International differences in IFRS policy choice: A research note. *Accounting and Business Research*, 40(2), 173-187.
- lxiii. Li, S. (2010). Does mandatory adoption of international financial reporting standards in the European Union reduce the cost of equity capital? *The Accounting Review*, 85 (2): 607–636.
- lxiv. Lin, S. (2012). Discussion on The Determinants and Consequences of Heterogeneous IFRS Compliance Levels Following Mandatory IFRS Adoption: Evidence from a Developing Country. *Journal of International Accounting Research*. 11 (1), 113– 118.
- lxv. Liu, C., Sia, C-L., & Wei, K-K. (2008). Adopting organizational virtualization in B2B firms: An empirical study in Singapore. *Information and Management*, 45(7), 429-437
- lxvi. Marshall, C. & Rossman, G.B. (2015). *Thiết kế nghiên cứu định tính*. Nhà xuất bản Kinh tế TP.HCM (Fifth edition).
- lxvii. Mathieson, K., Peacock, E. & Chin, W.W. (2001) *Extending the Technology Acceptance Model: The Influence of Perceived User Resources*. *Advances in Information Systems*, 32, 86-112.
- lxviii. Mir, M.Z., & Rahaman, A.S. (2004). The adoption of international accounting standards in Bangladesh. *Accounting Auditing and Accountability Journal*, 18(6), 816-841.
- lxix. Moons, I. & De Pelsmacker, P (2015). An Extended Decomposed Theory of Planned Behaviour to Predict the Usage Intention of the Electric Car: A Multi-Group Comparison. *Sustainability (MDPI)*, 7(5) 6212-6245.